

Nonlinear shear behavior of rock joints using a linearized implementation of the Barton-Bandis model

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Abstract

Experiments on rock joint behavior have shown that joint surface roughness is mobilized under shearing, inducing dilation and resulting in nonlinear joint shear strength and shear stress vs. shear displacement behavior. The Barton-Bandis (B-B) joint model provides the most realistic prediction for the nonlinear shear behavior of rock joints. The B-B model accounts for asperity roughness and strength through the joint roughness coefficient JRC and joint wall compressive strength JCS parameters. Nevertheless, many computer codes for rock engineering analysis still use the constant shear strength parameters from the linear Mohr-Coulomb (M-C) model, which is only appropriate for smooth and non-dilatant joints. This limitation prevents fractured rock models from capturing the nonlinearity of joint shear behavior. To bridge the B-B and the M-C models, this paper aims to provide a linearized implementation of the B-B model using a tangential technique to obtain the equivalent M-C parameters that can satisfy the nonlinear shear behavior of rock joints. These equivalent parameters, namely the equivalent *tangent* apparent cohesion,

friction angle, and dilation angle, are then converted into their *mobilized* forms to account for the mobilization and degradation of *JRC* under shearing. The conversion is done by expressing *JRC* in the equivalent tangent parameters as functions of joint shear displacement using proposed hyperbolic and logarithmic functions at the pre- and post-peak regions of shear displacement, respectively. Likewise, the pre- and post-peak joint shear stiffnesses are derived so that a complete shear stress-shear displacement relationship can be established. Verifications of the linearized implementation of the B-B model show that the shear stress-displacement curves, the dilation behavior, and the shear strength envelopes of rock joints are consistent with available experimental and numerical results.

Keywords

Rock joints; Joint shear behavior; Friction and dilation; Barton-Bandis model; Equivalent Mohr-Coulomb parameters

1. Introduction

Rock masses contain various types of discontinuities, such as bedding planes, joints, shear zones, and faults, that distinguish them from other materials. Joints are common and widespread in rocks, and unless they are healed and mineralized, joints have weakening effects on the strength of rock masses because they do not have tensile resistance and their shear strength is usually much smaller compared to the intact rock matrix (Priest, 1993; Singhal and Gupta, 2010). In a fractured rock mass, the shear behavior of rock joints is particularly important because it dominantly controls the deformability, strength, and hence the stability of the rock mass. For example, the conditions

for slip on major pervasive features in fractured rock masses, such as block sliding from a slope or block falling in an underground excavation, are not only controlled by the shear strength of the particular joint but also by its dilation along asperities under shearing (Brady and Brown, 2006....there are many before these). This dilation is caused by the mobilization of joint surface roughness, and it will cause nonlinearity in the shear strength, and strain hardening and strain softening in the shear behavior of rock joints. Therefore, it is essential for fractured rock models to take into account this nonlinearity so that realistic response of fractured rock masses can be accurately predicted, leading to the economical and reliable design and analysis of excavations and structures in rocks.

Extensive laboratory experiments on rock joint behavior from the early 1960s to date have shown that the shear behavior of rock joints is nonlinear (e.g., Barton and Choubey, 1977; Bandis et al., 1981; Barton, 1982; Barton et al., 1985; Indraratna and Haque, 2000; Hencher and Richards, 2015; Barton, 2016). The relationships between joint shear stress τ and normal stress σ_n in the τ vs. σ_n axes are also more accurately represented by a non-linear relationship than a linear one (Barton, 1973; Bandis et al., 1981; Barton, 1982; Barton et al., 1985). These previous studies have also shown that the nonlinear shear behavior of rock joints is significantly affected by the dilation-induced joint roughness.

Surprisingly, and as pointed out by Barton (2016), the joint roughness and wall strength parameters, known as the contributing parameters to the nonlinearity of the shear strength of rock joints, were initially ignored and rejected by leading researchers in reservoir geomechanics, following development of the parameters in rock mechanics in the 1970's. Barton (2016) also indicated that the widespread use of linear behavior assumptions could lead to errors in reservoir

interpretation since joint roughness-induced behaviors such as dilation, aperture increase, and permeability increase, **and also non-linear closure reversing the above**, were effectively ignored.

Patton (1966) was one of the first to consider the effect of joint roughness on the nonlinear shear behavior of rock joints by conducting a series of direct shear tests on saw-tooth triangular joints. Dilation is seen when the shear displacement occurs on these specimens, which then induces the joint surface to move up the inclined faces. He proposed a bilinear shear strength criterion consisting of two linear segments intersecting a normal stress called the transition stress. The shear strength of a joint is governed by the sliding along the joint asperities when the normal stress is less than the transitional stress, and by the partial shearing through of asperities when the normal stress is above the transition stress. Ladanyi and Archambault (1969) improved Patton's model by developing a shear strength criterion that considers simultaneous sliding and shearing of rock joints instead of separating the two mechanisms. However, the model is still challenging to implement due to the difficulty to obtain the transitional stress and the inclination angle parameters for irregular joint surfaces. Goodman (1976) was the first to develop a rock joint model in the general framework of the finite element method, which later stimulated rock mechanical researchers to enhance the application of joint models in numerical modeling. Unfortunately, Goodman's model did not consider the effect of surface roughness degradation under shearing.

The Barton-Bandis (B-B) joint model is currently the most realistic empirical model for predicting shear failure behavior of rough joints (Barton, 1973; Barton and Choubey, 1977; Bandis, 1980; Barton et al., 1985). In the B-B model, the **peak** shear strength of a rock joint is determined by the following criterion:

$$\tau = \sigma_n \tan \left[JRC \log_{10} \left(\frac{JCS}{\sigma_n} \right) + \phi_r \right] \quad (1)$$

where JRC is the joint roughness coefficient, JCS is the joint wall compressive strength and ϕ_r is the joint residual friction angle. The main advantages of the B-B model are: 1) it has been established based on and extensively verified against a wide range of experimental results, 2) the parameters involved have real physical meanings, and 3) the parameters can be easily determined using simple index tests. In addition, the B-B model has been implemented since 1985 as an option in the Universal Distinct Element Code (UDEC) developed by Peter Cundall (Itasca, 2014). The B-B model takes into account the increase in shear strength due to the mobilization of surface roughness (or strain hardening) during pre-peak shearing and its reduction (or strain softening) due to asperity degradation during post-peak shearing (Barton, 1982). By considering the pre- and post-peak behaviors, shear stress-shear displacement curves can be formulated for a wide range of input data, using Barton's dimensionless mobilized JRC concept (See Fig. 1, dotted line). This is an important part of the B-B model.

Due to its simplicity, rock mechanics engineers are still accustomed to use the linear Mohr-Coulomb (M-C) failure criterion for modeling fractured rock mass behavior (Bhasin and Barton, 1997), particularly in the continuum modeling approach. In addition, due to the historical development of rock mechanics, many stability analyses of excavations in jointed rock masses still use strength parameters in terms of cohesion and friction angle from the M-C failure criterion. The M-C criterion relates the shear stress τ and the normal stress σ_n at failure as

$$\tau = c + \sigma_n \tan \phi \quad (2)$$

where c is the cohesion intercept and ϕ is the friction angle. Needless to say, the M-C criterion is linear in the τ versus σ_n axes, and gives constant cohesion and friction angle, and does not consider the mobilization and reduction of joint surface roughness. Therefore, unlike in the B-B model, the strain hardening and strain softening behaviors of rock joints is not captured in the linear and perfectly-plastic M-C model (Fig. 1, solid line).

The shear strength criterion in the B-B model (Eq. (1)) is nonlinear and plots as a curved failure surface in the τ vs. σ_n axes. Fig. 2 shows plots of the B-B failure criterion as functions of different values of JRC and for typical values of $JCS = 50$ MPa and $\phi_t = 30^\circ$. With increasing JRC and σ_n , the B-B criterion becomes more curved and nonlinear. For $JRC = 0$, the B-B criterion corresponds to the M-C criterion with $\phi = \phi_t$ (cohesion is assumed zero). It should be noted that as the normal stress climbs towards the value of JCS , increased confined strength is assumed. The diameter of the **relevant** Mohr circle ($\sigma_1 - \sigma_3$) should replace JCS according to recommendations given by Barton (1976).

Nevertheless, despite the capability of the B-B model to characterize the nonlinear shear behavior of rock joints, many legacy computer codes for rock engineering analysis still use the linear M-C model. Among others, these computer codes are Abaqus (Simulia, 2012), FLAC (Itasca, 2011) and PLAXIS (Plaxis bv, 2016). Thus, given the need for realistic joint modeling, it will be beneficial if the B-B model can be implemented in these computer codes by directly linking the existing linear M-C joint models with the non-linear B-B model. This link can be achieved by obtaining the *equivalent* M-C parameters by “**multi-linearization**” of the B-B values. In addition,

the equivalent mobilized shear strength parameters can also be obtained to account for joint roughness mobilization and reduction as a function of shear displacement as was done by Barton (1982). In this way, the benefit of the simplicity of implementation of the linear M-C model in legacy computer codes can be coupled with the advanced **though quite simply understood** capabilities of the nonlinear B-B model.

2. Methods of linearization

There are two approaches to obtain mathematically equivalent *linear* M-C parameters from the *nonlinear* B-B failure criterion (Fig. 3), namely: (1) the equivalent *tangent* friction angle ϕ and cohesion c_t given, respectively, by the slope and intercept of the tangent to the nonlinear failure surface at the current **(effective)** normal stress, and (2) the equivalent *secant* friction angle ϕ and zero cohesion, given by drawing an intersecting line from the origin to the current **(effective)** normal stress at the failure surface. The two concepts to obtain the linear failure parameters are illustrated in Fig. 3. As can be seen, due to the nonlinearity in the rock joint shear failure behavior, the friction angles in both approaches are not constant but vary with normal stress. In the equivalent tangent approach, a non-zero cohesion is obtained, which is purely an apparent cohesion value that results from the linearization as joints do not have cohesive strength, unless with extremely steep steps, as where a secondary joint set is crossed by the **previously formed** continuous primary joint set.

As an example of the secant linearization concept, Fig. 4 shows the variation of the equivalent secant friction angle ϕ_s from the B-B model for different *JRC* values at *JCS* = 50 MPa and $\phi_t = 30^\circ$. As indicated, ϕ_s is not constant but decreases with the increase in normal stress due

to the nonlinearity of the relationship between shear strength and normal stress. From Fig. 4, it can also be seen that when $\sigma_n < JCS$, the equivalent secant friction angle ϕ_s is larger than $\phi_t = 30^\circ$ for $JRC > 0$, again due to the additional friction provided by the dilation along the asperities.

3. Linearization of the B-B model

The B-B model is linearized using a similar approach to the tangential technique shown in Fig. 3 to obtain the equivalent M-C parameters that can satisfy the nonlinear shear behavior of rock joints. These equivalent tangent parameters, namely the equivalent tangent cohesion, friction angle, and dilation angle, are then converted into their mobilized forms to account for the mobilization (during hardening) and degradation (during softening) of JRC under shearing. The full tangential linearization of the B-B model involves two steps: (1) deriving the equivalent linear tangent parameters from the B-B shear failure criterion, and (2) relating these equivalent linear parameters to Barton's (1982) mobilized roughness and shear displacement relations in the hardening and softening regimes.

3.1. Deriving the equivalent tangent parameters c_t , ϕ_t , and ψ_t

The equivalent tangent parameters can be derived by relating c and ϕ from the conventional M-C model to JRC , JCS and ϕ_t from the B-B model. In the literature, these equivalent parameters may have appeared in different forms and have been called instantaneous strength parameters (Deb, 2012; Liu et al., 2014). Adopting the same shearing strength as in the B-B model, the peak shearing strength in the equivalent M-C model can be expressed as

$$\tau_t = c_t + \sigma_n \tan \phi_t \quad (3)$$

where c_t is the equivalent tangent cohesion and ϕ is the equivalent tangent friction angle expressed as

$$\phi_t = JRC \log_{10} \left(\frac{JCS}{\sigma_n} \right) + \phi \quad (4)$$

Using Eq. (3) and Eq. (4), the inclination of the tangent to the nonlinear failure surface at the current normal stress σ_n in the B-B model is expressed as

$$\tan \phi_t = \frac{d\tau}{d\sigma_n} = \frac{d}{d\sigma_n} \left\{ \sigma_n \tan \left[JRC \log_{10} \left(\frac{JCS}{\sigma_n} \right) + \phi_r \right] \right\} \quad (5)$$

By using the product rule

$$(f \cdot g)' = f' \cdot g + f \cdot g' \quad (6)$$

and by setting

$$f = \sigma_n \quad \text{and} \quad g = \tan \left[JRC \log_{10} \left(\frac{JCS}{\sigma_n} \right) + \phi_r \right] \quad (7)$$

the first term on the right hand side of Eq. (6) becomes

$$f' \cdot g = \tan \left[JRC \log_{10} \left(\frac{JCS}{\sigma_n} \right) + \phi_r \right] = A \quad (8)$$

To obtain $f \cdot g'$, the following chain rule can be used

$$\frac{du}{dx} = \frac{du}{dv} \cdot \frac{dv}{dx} \quad (9)$$

By setting

$$u = \tan v, \quad v = JRC \log_{10} \left(\frac{JCS}{\sigma_n} \right) + \phi_r, \quad \text{and} \quad x = \sigma_n \quad (10)$$

the terms on the right-hand side of Eq. (9) can be expanded as

$$\frac{du}{dv} = 1 + \tan^2 v = 1 + \tan^2 \left[JRC \log_{10} \left(\frac{JCS}{\sigma_n} \right) + \phi_r \right] = 1 + A^2 \quad (11)$$

and

$$\frac{dv}{dx} = -\frac{JRC}{\sigma_n \ln 10} \quad (12)$$

Using Eqs. (9) – (12), the second term in Eq. (6) can be expressed as

$$f \cdot g' = -(1 + A^2) \frac{JRC}{\ln 10} = -B \quad (13)$$

Note that all quantities are in radians. Finally, by using Eqs. (8) and (13) **Error! Reference source not found.**, Eq. (5) becomes

$$\tan \phi_t = \tan \left[JRC \log_{10} \left(\frac{JCS}{\sigma_n} \right) + \phi_r \right] - (1 + A^2) \frac{JRC}{\ln 10} = A - B \quad (14)$$

and hence the equivalent tangent friction angle becomes

$$\phi_t = \arctan(A - B) \quad (15)$$

The equivalent tangent cohesion c_t can be found by equating Eqs. (1) and (2) in Section 1, with the use of Eq. (14), as

$$c_t = \sigma_n B \quad (16)$$

According to Maksimovic (1996), the essential components of the shear strength of rock joints consist of cohesion c , friction angle ϕ , and dilation angle ψ . Using this principle, Eq. (3) can be rewritten as

$$\tau_t = c_t + \sigma_n \tan(\phi_t + \psi_t) \quad (17)$$

and hence the equivalent tangent dilation angle ψ is simply given by

$$\psi_t = \phi_t - \phi_r \quad (18)$$

The next step is to relate the equivalent tangent parameters derived above to the roughness-shear displacement relationships during hardening and softening, and converting the peak parameters from the *constant* forms to the *mobilized* forms.

3.2. Relating the equivalent tangent parameters to roughness-shear displacement relation

To relate c_t , ϕ_t and ψ_t to the joint roughness coefficient JRC vs. shear displacement Δu relations, two analytical curve-fitting functions are proposed to smooth out the discrete and piecewise-linear paired values of JRC_m/JRC_p vs. $\Delta u/\Delta u_p$ developed by Barton (1982) as shown in Fig. 5. The parameters JRC_p and Δu_p correspond to the peak values of JRC and Δu at the peak

shear strength, respectively. Meanwhile, the parameter JRC_m corresponds to the *mobilized* values of JRC that vary according to the level of Δu relative to its peak value Δu_p .

For the shear displacement in the pre-peak strain hardening region, $\Delta u \leq \Delta u_p$, a hyperbolic function is proposed to capture the mobilization of joint roughness up to JRC_p . The function is expressed as

$$\left(\frac{JRC_m}{JRC_p} \right) = \frac{a(\Delta u / \Delta u_p)}{1 + b(\Delta u / \Delta u_p)} \quad (19)$$

where a and b are the constants to be determined to fit through the discrete values given by Barton (1982). For the shear displacement in the post-peak strain softening region, $\Delta u > \Delta u_p$, a logarithmic function is proposed to capture the reduction of the roughness until it approximately reaches the residual value ($JRC = 0$). The function is expressed as

$$\left(\frac{JRC_m}{JRC_p} \right) = m \ln \left(\frac{\Delta u}{\Delta u_p} \right) + n \quad (20)$$

where m and n are also the constants to be determined from the discrete values.

3.2.1. The pre-peak hyperbolic function

Two nonzero sets of data points are required: one at the start of dilation at $\Delta u / \Delta u_p = 0.3$, and the other at the peak displacement at $\Delta u / \Delta u_p = 1.0$. For the sake of derivation, all data points on the y-axis in Fig. 5 will be increased by ϕ_v / i , where i represents the effect of irregular asperities on the fracture surface and is defined as $i = JRC \log(JCS / \sigma_n)$, so that JRC_m / JRC_p will start from zero. Eq. (19) can be rewritten as

$$y = \frac{a x}{1 + b x} \quad (21)$$

where $y = JRC_m / JRC_p$ and $x = \Delta u / \Delta u_p$. Examining Eq. (21) at $x = 0.3$ and $x = 1.0$ gives

$$\text{at } x = 0.3, \quad \frac{\phi_r}{i} (1 + 0.3 b) = 0.3 a \quad (22)$$

$$\text{at } x = 1.0, \quad \left(1 + \frac{\phi_r}{i}\right) (1 + b) = a \quad (23)$$

Multiplying Eq. (23) by 0.3 and subtracting the resulting equation from Eq. (22), the constant b can be solved as

$$b = \frac{7}{3} \frac{\phi_r}{i} - 1 \quad (24)$$

The constant a can then be obtained from Eq. (21) as

$$a = \frac{10}{3} \frac{\phi_r}{i} (1 + 0.3 b) \quad (25)$$

By substituting the values of a and b back into Eq. (19), the *apparent* JRC_m will be obtained. The *true* JRC_m in the pre-peak strain hardening region is then given by subtracting $(\phi_r / i) JRC_p$ from the *apparent* JRC_m which gives

$$JRC_{m_pre} = \left[\frac{7(1 + \phi_r / i) \Delta u / \Delta u_p}{3 - (3 - 7 \phi_r / i) \Delta u / \Delta u_p} - 1 \right] \frac{\phi_r}{i} JRC_p \quad (26)$$

3.2.2. The post-peak logarithmic function

To develop the logarithmic function in the post-peak region, the standard curve fitting procedure in Excel can be used. It gives

$$JRC_{m_post} = \left[-0.217 \ln \left(\frac{\Delta u}{\Delta u_p} \right) + 1 \right] JRC_p \quad (27)$$

The constants $m = -0.217$ and $n = 1.0$ are fixed values and do not depend on the joint parameters (e.g., JRC , JCS , and ϕ_t).

By substituting JRC_{m_pre} from Eq. (26) and JRC_{m_post} from Eq. (27) into the equivalent tangent parameters c_t , ϕ_t and ψ_t in Eqs. (16), (15) and (18), respectively, the desired mobilized equivalent M-C parameters c_m , ϕ_m and ψ_m , can be obtained for the pre- and post-peak regions. Consequently, the mobilization and degradation of the asperities, signifying the strain hardening and strain softening shear behavior of rock joints, can now be represented in terms of the M-C parameters. When these mobilized parameters are implemented in a constitutive model for rock joints that uses constant M-C parameters, e.g., the ubiquitous joint model in the computer code Fast Lagrangian Analysis of Continua (FLAC) developed by Itasca (2011), they can enhance the capability of the linear M-C model to portray the nonlinear shear behavior of rock joints.

3.3. Deriving the joint shear stiffness

To develop a constitutive relationship between the shear stress τ and shear displacement Δu , it is also necessary to derive the shear stiffness K_s in the regions of the pre- and post-peak shear displacement. After replacing JRC in Eq. (1) with JRC_{m_pre} and JRC_{m_post} for the pre- and post-peak regions, respectively, K_s in both regions can be obtained by taking the derivative of the

resulting τ_m with respect to Δu , i.e., $K_s = \partial \tau_m / \partial \Delta u$. Having worked on the derivation, the pre-peak shear stiffness for the region of $\Delta u \leq \Delta u_p$ can be obtained as

$$K_{s_pre} = \log\left(\frac{JCS}{\sigma_n}\right) \frac{\pi}{180} \sigma_n \sec^2 \left[JRC_{m_pre} \log\left(\frac{JCS}{\sigma_n}\right) + \phi_r \right] \frac{a \Delta u_p}{(b \Delta u + \Delta u_p)^2} JRC_p \quad (28)$$

while the post-peak shear stiffness for the region of $\Delta u > \Delta u_p$ can also be obtained as

$$K_{s_post} = \log\left(\frac{JCS}{\sigma_n}\right) \frac{\pi}{180} \sigma_n \sec^2 \left[JRC_{m_post} \log\left(\frac{JCS}{\sigma_n}\right) + \phi_r \right] \frac{m}{\Delta u} JRC_p \quad (29)$$

In summary, the mobilized equivalent tangent parameters c_m , ϕ_m and ψ_m , and the shear stiffnesses K_{s_pre} and K_{s_post} for the pre- and post-peak regions of shear displacement have been derived. These are the parameters for the linearized B-B model that can now be implemented in the linear M-C model so that the nonlinear shear behavior of rock joints can be modeled. The next section will verify the ability of the linearized B-B model to predict joint shear behavior against experimental and numerical results from the literature. The equations presented above are programmed in Excel and used in the validation of the proposed equivalent linear implementation of the B-B model. Research is being conducted to implement the linearized B-B model into the built-in ubiquitous joint model in FLAC (Itasca, 2011).

4. Verifications

Four cases from laboratory and numerical experiments of direct shear tests of rock joints are used to verify the linearized implementation of B-B model. The standard profiles of joint

surface roughness are shown to provide physical visualizations of the corresponding *JRC* values used in the verifications. These profiles were taken from Barton and Choubey (1977).

4.1. Verifications against experimental results

In this section, the linearized B-B model is verified against the experimental results from Bandis (1980), and Olsson and Barton (2001), who performed a series of direct shear tests on replicas of rock joints and on natural joints in granite, respectively. The properties of the joint samples from their experiments are presented in Table 1.

With respect to the experimental results from Bandis (1980), as shown in Fig. 6, the linearized B-B model is able to capture the general trend of shear behaviors of rock joints for all values of joint length and *JRC* with reasonable agreement. When joint roughness decreases, less shear strength is obtained (Fig. 6a) because the joint becomes less dilated (Fig. 6b), indicated by the decrease in the peak dilation angle (Fig. 6c). The linearized B-B model is also able to capture the effect of roughness reduction on the shear stress after the peak shear strength is reached. This strain softening behavior is more pronounced for $JRC = 13.6$ than when the joint is relatively smooth with $JRC = 10.4$, which is consistent with the experimental results (Fig. 6a). The effect of size of the joint sample is also captured. With the decrease in joint length L , the shear displacement corresponding to the peak shear stress is observed to decrease, steepening the pre-peak shear stiffness curve. This behavior is also consistent with the experimental results reported by other researchers (Barton and Choubey, 1977; Bandis et al., 1981).

Variations of the mobilized cohesion and friction angles with shear displacement for the corresponding joint samples are shown in Fig. 7. The cohesion and dilation angle hardening and softening behaviors in the pre-peak and post-peak regions, respectively, are captured by the linearized B-B model, as well as the increase in the peak values with the increase in JRC . As expected, the two parameters increase to their maximum values and then decrease in the softening part, in which a large amount of reduction in the mobilized cohesion is shown. Similar results have been reported by Roosta et al. (2006). It can be noted from Fig. 7 that the cohesion from the linearized B-B model can be smaller than zero – the minimum theoretical limit of joint cohesion – before the dilation starts. Mathematically, the negativity in cohesion is because the origin of the JRC_m/JRC_p curve starts at $-\phi/i$, which as defined by Eqs. (13) and (16) will cause c_m to start from a negative value. Physically, it may mean that cohesion still has “zero” influence on the shear strength of rock joints in the early stage of joint shear displacement, and that the shear strength of rock joints only depends on the friction angle. Nevertheless, it should be noted that the rate of cohesion change in this early displacement is positive, which is in accordance with the gradual increase in the value of JRC_m/JRC_p .

With respect to the experimental results from Olsson and Barton (2001), as shown in Fig. 8, the linearized B-B model can reproduce shear stress and dilation curves in good agreement with the test results. Even though the linearized B-B model overestimates the magnitude of the peak shear displacement and the shear stress following the failure (Fig. 8a), the model can closely capture the dilation behavior of the joint sample (Fig. 8b).

4.2. Verification against numerical results

The linearized B-B model is also verified against the numerical results from Nguyen and Selvadurai (1998), and Bahaaddini et al. (2013). The former performed shear tests of rock joints in the finite element code FRACON (Nguyen and Selvadurai, 1993, 1996) considering the asperity damage as a function of plastic work, while the latter conducted the tests in the discrete element code PCF2D (Itasca, 2008) using the so-called shear box genesis approach. The properties of the joint samples from the numerical experiments are presented in Table 2. The *JRC* values used in Bahaaddini et al. are the results from back-calculating the shear strength envelopes presented in Barton and Choubey (1977). Out of 10 *JRC* values used in the numerical experiments by Bahaaddini et al., only eight of them are verified in this section.

Fig. 9 shows the comparison plots between the shear behavior from the linearized B-B model and from Nguyen and Selvadurai (1998). The results for shear stress versus shear displacement, presented in Fig. 9a, show a close fit between the results derived from the linearized B-B model and from Nguyen and Selvadurai. The shear strength of the joint increases with the increase in the normal stress level, inducing more nonlinear post-peak strain softening behavior. This observation indicates that joints become more brittle at higher normal stress due to the asperities damage that weakens the joint, which is consistent with its shear strength behavior explained in Section 1 (see the explanation for Fig. 2). The comparison for the dilation-induced shear displacement is shown in Fig. 9b. Good agreement is obtained between the linearized B-B model and the numerical experiments within a certain extent of shear displacement (approximately at $\Delta u \leq 10$ mm). For $\Delta u > 10$ mm, the dilation curves from the linearized B-B model are overestimated compared to the numerical experiments. Nevertheless, the general trend of

decreasing dilation with increasing normal stress is evidently captured by the linearized B-B model.

Fig. 10 shows the comparison of the shear strength envelopes obtained from the linearized B-B model and Bahaaddini et al. (2013) for eight *JRC* values. The shear strength envelopes that resulted from the linearized B-B model match very well with those from the numerical results at various *JRC* and normal stress values. The nonlinearity in the strength envelopes is well captured by the linearized B-B model and is more pronounced for rough joints ($JRC > 10$) than for the relatively more planar joint ($JRC < 10$). Similarly, the trend for the peak dilation angle curves are also in good agreement with those from the numerical results (Fig. 11). These results show that the linearized B-B model can reproduce the realistic peak shear strength and peak dilation angle of real joint profiles.

5. Conclusions

A direct link between the linear M-C model and the nonlinear B-B model, called the linearized B-B model, was established using a tangential technique for predicting the shear behavior of rock joints. This linearization produces the equivalent tangent parameters that can be expressed in terms of the M-C parameters but consist of the joint parameters from the B-B model at the same time. The equivalent linear tangent apparent cohesion, friction and dilation parameters c_t , ϕ_t , and ψ_t were further related to joint roughness mobilization and reduction, converting the parameters from the constant forms to the mobilized forms. These mobilized equivalent parameters, namely the mobilized equivalent apparent cohesion c_m , dilation angle ψ_m , and friction angle ϕ_m , were related to shear displacement using the previously constituted discrete-paired

values of JRC_m/JRC_p vs. $\Delta u/\Delta u_p$ from the B-B joint model. These discrete points were smoothed out using the proposed continuous hyperbolic and logarithmic functions to get the mobilized roughness, JRC_m , that will govern the shear behaviors in the pre-peak strain hardening and post-peak strain softening regions, respectively. After substituting the resulting JRC_{m_pre} and JRC_{m_post} into the equation for τ and taking the derivative of the resulting τ_m with respect to Δu , the pre- and post-peak joint shear stiffnesses, K_{s_pre} and K_{s_post} , were derived. By doing this, a complete shear stress-shear displacement relationship can now be established and used in a constitutive model for rock joints. (Of course this is already available if using the fully non-linear B-B model, as coded in UDEC-BB).

Verifications against experimental and numerical direct shear test results showed that the linearized B-B model can reproduce realistic shear stress-displacement and dilation-induced shear displacement behaviors under variations of joint length, normal stress, and JRC values. The pre-peak strain hardening and the post-peak strain softening behaviors, induced by the mobilization and degradation of joint roughness under shearing, were well captured as well as the dilation behavior. The effect of decreasing joint length in reducing the amount of peak shear displacement and steepening the pre-peak shear stiffness is properly represented and is consistent with results reported in other literature. In addition, the non-linearity of the shear strength envelopes at various JRC and normal stress values is also reproduced well. The nonlinearity was seen to be more pronounced for rough joints than for planar ones, which is consistent with the verified numerical results.

The modeling and validation results showed that the formulation of the equivalent mobilized tangent parameters, as well as the pre-peak and post-peak shear stiffnesses in the

linearized B-B model are valid, serving their purpose to characterize the nonlinear shear behavior of rock joints. The linearized B-B model can be potentially applied in computer codes for fractured rock modeling that use the M-C based strain-hardening/softening constitutive model for rock joints. Therefore, neither the benefit of simplicity of the linear M-C model nor the advanced capability of the nonlinear B-B model is lost.

Conflict of interest

The authors confirm that there is no known conflict of interest associated with the work presented in this paper and there has been no significant financial support for this work that could have influenced its outcome.

Acknowledgments

The authors gratefully acknowledge support from the National Energy Technology Laboratory (NETL), U.S. Department of Energy, for partially funding this research through the American Recovery and Reinvestment Act (ARRA) of 2009, Project No. DE-FE0002058.

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TABLES

Table 1

Properties of the joint samples used in the laboratory experiments by Bandis (1980), and Olsson and Barton (2001)

Property	Bandis (1980)	Olsson and Barton (2001)
L (cm)	18, 12, 6	20
JRC	11.8, 13.6, 16.8	9.7
JCS (MPa)	2	169
σ_n (MPa)	0.015	2
ϕ_t ($^\circ$)	32	31

Table 2

Properties of the joint samples used in the numerical experiments by Nguyen and Selvadurai (1998) and Bahaaddini et al. (2013)

Property	Nguyen and Selvadurai (1998)	Bahaaddini et al. (2013)
L (cm)	15	10
JRC	9.0	5.8 – 18.7
JCS (MPa)	28.0	27.4
σ_n (MPa)	1, 2, 5	0.5, 1 - 5
ϕ_t ($^\circ$)	37.0	37.6

LIST OF FIGURE CAPTIONS

- Fig. 1.** Illustration of a shear stress vs. shear displacement curve from the mobilized *JRC* concept based on specific input data. It is compared with the closest (bi-linear) M-C model.
- Fig. 2.** The B-B failure criterion for different *JRC* values, $JCS = 50$ MPa and $\phi_t = 30^\circ$.
- Fig. 3.** Illustration of the equivalent *tangent* friction angle ϕ_t and cohesion c_t , and equivalent *secant* friction angle ϕ_s at the current stress σ_n from the nonlinear B-B model.
- Fig. 4.** Equivalent linear secant friction angle ϕ_s from the nonlinear B-B model for different *JRC* values, $JCS = 50$ MPa and $\phi_t = 30^\circ$.
- Fig. 5.** Concept of joint roughness mobilization (Barton, 1982).
- Fig. 6.** Comparisons of (a) shear stress, (b) dilation, and (c) dilation angle vs. shear displacement from the equivalent linear implementation of the B-B model against experimental results from Bandis (1980).
- Fig. 7.** Plots of mobilized equivalent (a) cohesion and (b) friction angle vs. shear displacement for different *JRC*-values for Bandis's experiments (Bandis, 1980).
- Fig. 8.** Comparisons of (a) shear stress and (b) dilation vs. shear displacement displacement from the equivalent linear implementation of the B-B model against the experimental results from Olsson and Barton (2001).
- Fig. 9.** Comparisons of (a) shear stress and (b) dilation vs. shear displacement from the linearized implementation of the B-B model against the numerical results from Nguyen and Selvadurai (1998).
- Fig. 10.** Comparison of the shear strength envelopes from the linearized implementation of the B-B model against the numerical results from Bahaaddini et al. (2013).
- Fig. 11.** Comparison of the peak dilation angle curves from the linearized implementation of the B-B model against the numerical results from Bahaaddini et al. (2013).

FIGURES

Fig. 1. Illustration of a shear stress vs. shear displacement curve from the mobilized *JRC* concept based on specific input data. It is compared with the closest (bi-linear) M-C model.

Fig. 2. The B-B failure criterion for different JRC values, $JCS = 50$ MPa and $\phi_r = 30^\circ$.

(A point for consideration: $JRC = 20$ has maybe never been measured for a rock joint. It *has* been measured in the case of artificial tension fractures. For these there is a remarkably high friction angle due to extreme (experimental) steepening of the strength envelope as the normal stress approaches zero. We could keep the $JRC = 20$ envelope in Figure 2 – if this explanation was included. Otherwise, just $JRC = 0, 5, 10, 15?$because it looks like there should be cohesion, but (miraculously) there is not: see figure here (from Barton, 1971)

Fig. 3. Illustration of the equivalent *tangent* friction angle ϕ_t and cohesion c_t , and equivalent *secant* friction angle ϕ_s at the current stress σ_n from the nonlinear B-B model.

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(c) DOES REPRODUCTION OF THESE LAST THREE FIGURES ADD ANYTHING USEFUL? IT WILL ADD DOUBT WHICH MAY OR MAY NOT BE JUSTIFIED.

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